

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

TOURISM AS A PROMISING SECTOR OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract

The article discusses the problems and prospects for the development of tourism in the Kyrgyz Republic for economic development, analyzes the dynamics of the volume of gross domestic product of the Kyrgyz Republic, the level of poverty in the Kyrgyz Republic, cash income of households in the EAEU countries, gross value added in the field of tourism activities in the Kyrgyz Republic.

Keywords: gross domestic product, poverty level, gross value added in the field of tourism activities, export of tourism services, import of tourism services.

The national economy of the Kyrgyz Republic is experiencing significant influences from global economic processes. To determine the level of economic development of the Kyrgyz Republic, we reviewed such macroeconomic indicators as the gross domestic product of the Kyrgyz Republic and the gross domestic product of the Kyrgyz Republic per capita.

The gross domestic product of the Kyrgyz Republic (in US dollars) grew by 46.7% in 2018-2022. At the same time, the gross domestic product of the Kyrgyz

Republic per capita increased by 21.6%. The consequences of the global lockdown of 2020 caused by the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on economic and social processes in the Kyrgyz Republic. Macroeconomic indicators showed economic contraction in 2020. However, in 2022, the volume of GDP in the Kyrgyz Republic increased and exceeded the level of 2019, amounting to 12,137.3 million US dollars in absolute terms [1] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of gross domestic product of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [1]

However, despite the restoration of macroeconomic indicators in the post-Covid period, the standard of living of the population continued to decline, as evi-

denced by the increase in the poverty level, which increased from 20.1% in 2019 to 33.2% in 2022, accordingly the number of poor people amounted to 2,333 162 people [2] (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Poverty level in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2019-2022

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [2]

Also, an analysis of the cash income of households in the Kyrgyz Republic shows a decline in the standard of living of the population. If we compare this indicator with the countries of the EAEU, this gives an assessment not in favor of the Kyrgyz Republic, since per

household member per month in 2021 they amounted to 79 US dollars versus 461 US dollars in Russia, 263 US dollars in Belarus, 162 US dollars USA in Kazakhstan, 151 US dollars in Armenia [3] (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Cash income of households in the EAEU countries for 2019-2021, per household member per month (US dollars)

Source: compiled according to data from the Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC) [3]

Tourism is one of the economic sectors that are developing dynamically. The main driving force behind the rapid development of tourism is the rapidly growing demand for exploring new places, changing visual images of nature, and outdoor recreation to restore economic and psychological health. For the development of the national economy of the Kyrgyz Republic, tourism is suitable as a priority industry for the Republic. Tourism is one of the highly promising sectors of the economy that are adaptive to global changes. Tourism based on the principles of sustainability can help solve many problems related not only to employment, but also to environmental degradation, primarily

the degradation of land and water resources, and biodiversity. The beneficial natural components of tourism development complement cultural and historical attractions and create the resource basis for the development of the sector [5, 6, 7]. If we add favorable conditions for investors to this, then we can bring tourism on a par with the leading sectors of the economy to stimulate the economic development of the regions of the republic and overcome poverty of the rural population. Despite the fact that over the two years of tourism recovery after the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, it has demonstrated good economic performance [8, 9, 10]. If we analyze the gross value added in the field of tourism

activities for 2019-2022, we can note that it increased by 12.1%, despite the fact that in 2020 it decreased by 37.6%. Although the share of tourism activity in GDP

in 2022 was still quite low compared to 2019 [4] (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Dynamics of gross value added in the field of tourism activities in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2019-2022
Source: compiled according to data from the NSC KR

Exports of tourism services in the Kyrgyz Republic regarding trips for 2019-2022 increased by 13.6%, amounting to 696.4 million US dollars in 2022, which is 3.6 times more than imports [4] (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Dynamics of export and import of tourism services (trips) in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2019-2022, million US dollars

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [4]

Although the decrease in both exports and imports of tourism services in the Kyrgyz Republic during the COVID-19 pandemic was significant, the volume of imports during the period under review decreased by 48.6%. This trend has a beneficial effect on the increasing contribution of tourism to GDP and its positive impact on the socio-economic development of the republic. In addition, it gives impetus to the development of the transport industry.

When characterizing tourism, the components of the tourism product are determined, namely:

- tourist attractions of the area (for example: environment, monuments, interesting architectural sites, national parks, botanical gardens, shopping centers, cultural and religious attractions, museums, as well as residents - their culture and customs);
- infrastructure of the area (accommodation, gastronomic base - restaurants, bars, cafes, transport -

taxis, buses, car rental, retail chain, service establishments, etc.);

- accessibility of the area (amount of transport, as well as infrastructure - roads, airports and ports, railway network);

- the image of the area, which exists in the minds of potential clients and significantly influences the subconscious desire to visit this particular area;

- price, which depends on many factors, namely: standard of services, time of year, amount of transport and others [13].

Tourism contributes to the development of the regions of the republic, their infrastructure, the construction of quality roads, and this process is reciprocal. The development of regions and overcoming poverty of the rural population is the primary task of the state and tourism can become a key link in this [11].

Integration into the global economic space can serve as a positive factor in the development of tourism

in the Kyrgyz Republic, which is facilitated by the territorial proximity of partner countries. The development of private entrepreneurship in tourism can stimulate self-employment of the rural population, create jobs in the regions of the republic, attract investment, thereby increasing the incomes of the rural population and reducing poverty.

The economic integration of the Kyrgyz Republic into the world economic space through the free movement of tourists, the movement of finances, and attracting investments could bring positive results for the development of the tourism sector. However, the consequences of tourists' stay should be assessed, conditions should be created and measures taken to preserve the environment. Environmental pollution from the growth of tourist flows should be minimized by carrying out special environmental measures, observing the generally accepted culture of behavior of both tourists and tourism service providers, creating conditions for "green" tourism. To do this, it is necessary to streamline the movement of tourists, prevent environmental pollution through the development of the activities of tourism enterprises in the organized sector, since professionally operating enterprises have special knowledge and experience in running the tourism business [12, 14].

Despite the growth of organizations involved in the tourism business, this is extremely insufficient to provide tourism services at a high level; individual entrepreneurs and individuals involved in tourist accommodation should be required to improve the quality of service, comply with environmental measures, and it is also necessary to strengthen control on the part of environmental organizations for compliance with the rules of conducting tourism business, creating conditions for tourists to stay, etc. [15, 16].

Thus, tourism as a potentially highly profitable sector of the economy requires attracting investment, attention from the state and can serve as an impetus for the economic development of regions and a factor in overcoming poverty in the rural population.

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